

ISOLATION OF URSOLIC ACID FROM *VINCA ROSEA* LINN.

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Ursolic acid, a 2-hydroxy-17-carboxy acid of α -amyrin series, has been isolated from the whole plant of *Vinca rosea* Linn.

During the isolation of alkaloidal constituents from the whole plant of *Vinca rosea* Linn., a considerable amount of a light yellowish green amorphous solid was obtained. It has been now possible to isolate from the latter a triterpene derivative of α -amyrin series (yield 0.1%), proved to be identical with ursolic acid by direct comparison of their properties (Table I).

TABLE I

	Ursolic acid from <i>Vinca rosea</i> L.	Ursolic acid from <i>Verbena stricta</i> *
M. P.	280°	282°
Mol. formula	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃
Optical rotation	[α] _D ²⁸ = +65°.8	[α] _D ²⁵ = +65°.6
Crystalline form	Fine needles from ethyl alcohol.	Same.
Solubility	Insoluble in benzene, chloroform and soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate and ethyl alcohol.	Same
Colour reactions	In Liebermann and Burchard's test the chloroform layer turns pink which immediately changes to blue and on keeping turns green.	Same
Mol. formula and m.p. of methyl ursolate	C ₃₁ H ₅₀ O ₃ , 169°	C ₃₁ H ₅₀ O ₃ , 168.4°
Mol. formula and m.p. of acetylursolic acid	C ₃₃ H ₅₀ O ₄ , 263°	C ₃₃ H ₅₀ O ₄ , 282°

* King, Chatterjee and Parks, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc., Sci. Ed.*, 1950, 39, 593.

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

The dried and milled drug (1.0 kg.) was extracted with alcohol. The green alcoholic extract deposited an amorphous mass (A). The concentrated extract when poured into water deposited a further amount of solid materials (B). The supernatant reddish brown liquid was decanted off and worked up for the alkaloids (Chatterjee and Talapatra, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 20, 568).

Isolation of Ursolic Acid.—The light yellow amorphous fractions (A) and (B) (2.0 g.) were dissolved in alcohol and the alcoholic solution was treated with charcoal

* All the melting points recorded here are uncorrected.

and filtered. From the clear filtrate colorless needles (1.2 g., m.p. 268-74°) of ursolic acid separated out on cooling. On recrystallisation from alcohol fine needles of ursolic acid (m. p. 280°) were obtained. Further purification of the substance was done by its chromatography over alumina.

Ursolic acid (0.1 g.), dissolved in a mixture of ethyl acetate and acetone (2:1), was adsorbed in neutral alumina (32 cm × 2 cm). The chromatogram was developed and eluted with benzene and a mixture of benzene and ethyl acetate (Table II).

TABLE II

Eluents.	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Benzene	1-5	Nil
Benzene+10% ethyl acetate	6-10	Nil
Ethyl acetate	10-13	Nil
Ethyl acetate +5% alcohol	13-20	White solid, m p 280°

Fractions (13-20) crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and ethyl alcohol (1:1) in fine needles (yield 0.083 g.), m.p. 280°. (Found: C, 78.52; H, 10.64. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$: C, 78.95; H, 10.52%).

An alcoholic solution of the substance showed no characteristic change in colour with ferric chloride solution nor did it liberate iodine when a solution of ursolic acid was added to a solution of a mixture of potassium iodide and potassium iodate. The optical rotation of ursolic acid was observed in 1*N* alcoholic KOH solution.

Acetyl Derivative.—Ursolic acid (0.1 g.) was refluxed with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and pyridine (3 drops) for 5 hours. The reaction product was then added to crushed ice. The white flocculent mass separating was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol when fine needles of acetylursolic acid (yield 0.095 g., m.p. 283°) were obtained. (Found: C, 77.50; H, 9.97. Calc for $C_{32}H_{50}O_4$: C, 77.10; H, 10.04%).

Methyl Ursolate.—Ursolic acid (0.1 g.) on methylation with diazomethane in methanol furnished silky needles of its methyl ester (yield 0.07 g.), m.p. 112-14°. It was subsequently purified by chromatographic resolution over alumina (25 cm × 2 cm) using petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and benzene as eluents, collected in fractions of 15 c.c. each (Table III).

TABLE III

Eluents.	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Pet. ether	1	Nil
Do	2-5	Non-crystallisable slimy mass.
Do	6-7	Nil
Benzene	8	White solid, m.p. 162
Do	9-12	White solid crystallised from methanol; m.p 168°
Do	13-15	Nil

Fractions 8-12 were all mixed together and crystallised from dilute methanol (50%) when silky needles of methyl ursolate separated (yield 0.06 g.), m.p. 169° (Found: C, 79.43; H, 10.92; OMe, 6.54. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.57; H, 10.63 OMe, 6.59%).

Benzoyl Derivative.--Ursolic acid (0.2 g.) was refluxed with benzoyl chloride (5 c.c.) and pyridine (0.1 c.c.). The reaction product was poured into crushed ice when a white flocculent mass separated. It was crystallised from benzene in colorless crystals with sandy touch (yield 0.05 g.), m.p. 216-18°. (Found: C, 79.64; H, 9.56. $C_{37}H_{52}O_4$ requires C, 79.28; H, 9.28%).

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